

The combination of wetted prilled urea and VRA nitrogen application technology on dairy farms: Is it worth it? The first 7 months results from 6 irrigated Australian dairy farms

Stewart Spilsbury
FOO Technologies, PO Box 892, Newry, Victoria 3859, Australia

Abstract

Background: This study looks at six irrigated dairy farms in Victoria, Australia that have entered into a commercial agreement to use VRA plus wetted prills technology for two years to try to reduce nitrogen inputs and costs. The author has attempted to quantify the impact of changing from an “ad-hoc” granular nitrogen application to a “wetted prills/VRA application” on a commercial scale.

Methods: Weekly paddock based pasture measurements were taken using a sonar Automatic Pasture Reader (APR) for the past year and will continue for the next two years of the trial. Yield maps were created using the APR data for each of the 300 odd paddocks, and nitrogen inputs are weighed onto each farm using a Kuhn spreader fitted with scales. This data is aggregated over all the farms versus the previous year’s data.

Results: The budget was that the farms would reduce their nitrogen inputs from an average 249 kg/N/Ha down to 152 kg/N/ha, a reduction of 39%..

Discussion: If the budgeted reductions to nitrogen inputs (39%) and costs (30%) can be achieved without any loss to pasture production, this will provide a real pathway for irrigated dairy farms to significantly improve the environmental impact of their nitrogen applications without impinging on-farm profits.

Conclusion: The early indications are very promising and a full set of results will be submitted at 12 months and again at two years.

Background

This study involves six irrigated dairy farms in the Macalister Irrigation District (MID) in Gippsland, Victoria, Australia. The farms have entered into a commercial agreement to change from using ‘ad hoc’ applications of granular fertiliser urea to using Wetted prilled urea combined with variable rate application (VRA) for two years. Over this period, reductions in nitrogen (N) inputs, pasture yield, costs, milk production, and any related issues are being assessed. Historically, each of the farms had different systems to decide how and when to apply urea, although all were receiving weekly growth rate and cover data from FOO Technologies. Historical data on MS production, tonnes DM grown, N application by paddock and feed test data exists for all farms and is used as the base data set. It was evident that growth rate variation was closely related to the frequency of N applications as well as soil moisture levels. In addition, it seemed that there was no relationship between nitrogen application rates and tonnage of DM grown; more-over high N inputs did not always translate to high tonnes grown. Likewise, total N usage being used on some farms seemed excessive. In addition to improving N Utilisation Efficiency (NUE), this study is attempting identify factors and conditions associated with poor NUEs.

Methods

Weekly paddock based pasture DM measurements have been made for 2-5 years previously on the 6 farms, using a sonar Automatic Pasture Reader (APR) to determine tonnes DM grown, as part of the consulting service provided to the farms by FOO Technologies, and these are continuing. This has allowed variation in pasture yield at a whole farm level, year on year to be compared with the trial data. In addition, historical milk production numbers for all farms has been collated for comparison with the current year’s production. Two of the farms have also had weekly soil moisture readings taken over all paddocks, using a Geonics EM38 Mk2. Soil moisture has been charted against pasture growth during the irrigation period of the trial.

Figure 1. Honda 4WD bike fitted with APR (Sonar) and Geonics EM38Mk2

All farms have had weekly pasture feed tests taken, to compare with historical feed tests over the same timeframe. Yield maps of individual paddocks were created using the APR height data for each of the 300-odd paddocks, to identify the stock camp areas where N applications could be reduced, and the low fertility areas which would respond well to higher N applications. The height data was divided into three equally-sized fractions for each paddock – low, medium and high, with the DM splits being driven purely by having equal proportions of each. This in turn was used to create the paddock-specific VRA maps, with three application rate sectors split inversely according to the pasture heights. That is, the high pasture stock camp areas received the lowest N application and the lowest height pasture regions received the highest N applications.

Figure 2. VRA map of Farm "M_B"

The spreading agreement with the contractor was based around twice weekly applications of N, following as close as possible behind the cows. This is significantly different to the ad-hoc N applications of the past. Rates set were based on the paddocks receiving 1kg urea per day of rotation. Typically, when using granular urea, this would be set at 2kg urea per day or 1 kg elemental nitrogen per day. The use of Wetted prilled urea technology allows us to considerably reduce this rate (Quin et al. 2015), (Spilsbury and Quin 2016) and (Spilsbury & Quin 2017). With the VRA technology, the N rate applied was varied one third up and down on this rate, based on pasture height. Note that newly sown or under-sown paddocks had 50% higher rates of N applied. The conduct of this multi-farm trial required the contractor to purchase a VRA capable tractor-mounted spreader, which was then fitted with a Wetted prilled urea technology kit to enable very even application of very low rates of application of urea prills (rather than urea granules). The decision was made to purchase a VRA capable Kuhn Axis 50.2 spreader (fitted with scales) and a John Deere 6130R tractor. A 2-year, full service-level agreement between 12 farms (6 in the trial) and the contractor was implemented. The urea prills were imported by the farmer group, in one tonne bags direct onto farm. The prills and spreading gear were all in place by the 1st November; the change to the new system was then made.

Figure 3. The Kuhn Axis 50.2 Spreader with Wetted prilled urea technology kit fitted

Results

The original calculations showed it was possible for all farms to reduce their N inputs by 50% and achieve a cost saving of 30%. The results at the 7-month mark of the first year are significantly less on average, but one farm has achieved a significant reduction in N inputs but no cost savings. Unexpectedly, because the farmers liked the response to N they were seeing and could get the trial contractor to the farm on a much more 'on-demand' basis, most started requesting more frequent applications on N as Wetted prilled urea than they used to as granular urea. Typically the number of applications were 5 per year, but under the new system, the average has already surpassed 6 at the 7 month mark. Although they are tending to apply only a third as much N/ha each application as they used to, the increased frequency of application meant that the accumulated total YTD is more than anticipated. Also, because the farmers were used to having the fertiliser cost combined with the spreading cost as one invoice, not separately as was being done by the trial contractor, it took them a while to adjust to the fact that spreading itself was a significant part of the total cost. Hence their application costs rose considerably, especially as a premium is charged per ha for the Wetted prilled urea spreading.

The farmers have now realised that it is simply not necessary to increase the frequency of application compared to granular urea, and that it is up to them to decide individually just how much N they want to apply each time, compared to what they would have applied as granular urea. This will also be affected initially by the existing level of soil organic N fertility on individual farms. Over the last 2 months, application frequency on the 6 farms appears to be stabilising at closer to previous practice, and closer to the targeted 50% reduction in N application rate, meaning that cost savings are likely to be achieved in the second year.

Table 1. Nitrogen application YTD versus historical

Client	KG/N/Ha historic	KG/N/Ha YTD	Rounds YTD	N Projected reduction	Granular Urea \$/Tonne	Prilled Urea \$/tonne	Difference forecast
					\$550	\$490	
					Total Cost Historic (P.A)	Total Cost Now (Forecast)	
Farm "M_T"	276	102	6.7	63%	\$ 59,400	\$ 67,039	-\$ 7,639
Farm "M_B"	210	111	5.8	91%	\$ 38,165	\$ 55,300	-\$ 17,135
Farm "G"	182	143	6.8	135%	\$ 26,795	\$ 55,224	-\$ 28,429
Farm "MC_S"	174	110	6.1	109%	\$ 38,413	\$ 68,474	-\$ 30,062
Farm "MC_T"	180	102	5.8	97%	\$ 27,978	\$ 44,885	-\$ 16,906
Farm "L"	217	125	5.9	99%	\$ 42,810	\$ 64,271	-\$ 21,460
					\$ 233,561	\$ 355,193	
Average YTD		116	6.2				
Historic	206	198	Forecast				-\$ 121,632
		96%					Forecast cost difference.

A complicating factor for the farmers in the trial is that grass tonnages grown in the year to date have been well below the last five-year average. Lower rainfall, higher incidence of high temperatures, and sub-optimum utilisation of irrigation water has not helped. Some of the farmers in the trial group have no doubt tried to compensate for this through greater or more frequent N applications. However no farm has fed more supplements than in any previous year, and most farms are at their equal lowest supplements fed per cow on record with three farms having the lowest supplement input on record (Table 2). It is not abnormal in low pasture growth years for pasture utilisation to be higher compared to years when pasture growth rates are plentiful. In those good years, utilisation is often poorer. This is likely to be the reason why milk production has hardly changed at all (Table 2).

Table 2. Milk solids production, Supplements fed and Tonnes DM grown YTD versus historical

Client	Tonnes grown (Oct through April inclusive) Last years versus this year				Supplements Fed (Tonnes/cow) Last years versus this year					Total Milk Solids sent YTD (to 30th April) last years versus this year.				
	13_14	14_15	15_16	16_17	13_14	14_15	15_16	15_16	16_17	13_14	14_15	15_16	15_16	16_17
Farm "M_T"	1,895,415	1,705,529	1,933,080	1,752,546	2.3	2.8	2.6	2.3	2.2	338,360	347,499	364,588	364,588	345,711
Farm "M_B"	1,244,136	1,228,343	1,262,279	1,106,448		1.9	2.1		1.9	236,496	225,903	225,903	225,903	228,632
Farm "G"		1,249,466	1,471,322	1,274,657			2.1	1.6	1.4	155,684	175,001	175,127	175,127	169,054
Farm "MC_S"	1,647,259	1,503,912	1,683,860	1,512,996	2.1	1.8	1.9	2.1	1.9	205,450	216,926	242,083	242,083	198,385
Farm "MC_T"			1,175,311	982,236				2.0	1.6			148,718	148,718	148,444
Farm "L"			1,532,033	1,525,941			2.7	2.8	2.7	251,419	271,291	267,057	267,057	270,532

Table 3. Current season rainfall is only 86% of Historical YTD rainfall (BOM data)

Season	5 year Historical	16_17
Rainfall to end May (mm)	508	435

Despite the fact that the MID is an irrigated farming region, the impact of poor irrigation management, particularly under flood irrigation, impacts significantly on growth rates. The impact of running soil moisture levels below the 40% 'safe minimum' target on the two farms that were comprehensively monitored show that (i) every drop in soil moisture leads to a drop in DM production within 2 days (both farms, Figs 1 and 2); (ii) farm "L" has been irrigated sufficiently frequently from late December 2016 to keep moisture about 40% and therefore DM growth rates above 45 kg DM/ha/day (Fig. 1), and good production YTD (Table 1); and (iii) farm "M-B" (Fig. 2 below) has rarely had soil moistures even slightly above 30%, and consequently growth rates have suffered by comparison, falling below 20 kg DM/ha/day on one occasion, and giving lower production YTD (Table 1).

Graph 1. Soil moisture versus growth rate for farm "L"

Graph 2. Soil moisture versus growth rate for farm "M-B"

Feed analyses from farm "M-B" (Table 4) also show that in addition, the available ME has fallen significantly (due to the NDF limit being exceeded). By comparison, farm "L" shows only a small decrease.

Table 4. Pasture feed test results for farm "L" and farm "M-B";

Farm – "L"

Result	Historical Average	Average 16_17
ME	11.5	11.3
NDF	49.1	49.7
ME available (NDF limit)	176	172

Farm - "M-B"

Result	Historical Average	Average 16_17
ME	11.3	11.5
NDF	48.1	49.0
ME available (NDF limit)	189	178

Note: The average dairy cow can only eat around 7.5kg of NDF per day so this has a significant impact on ME intakes at times of high NDF.

Discussion and conclusions

As with all commercial scale trials involving multiple farms, the farmer's decisions made over the course of the trial can have unexpected impacts on the trial outcomes. Fortunately, the use of six different trials in this major study, and the combination of different measurements taken, have allowed 'cause and effect' to become increasingly clearly established, and indicate the likelihood of some strong conclusions being able to be drawn from the 2 year's data at the conclusion of the trial.

The results to date indicate the very strong interrelationships between the management of soil moisture levels through irrigation, N application and farm production, and specifically maintaining a minimum of 40% soil moisture and supplying adequate N.

There are also increasingly strong indications that with time the efficiency of fertiliser N can be very substantially improved through the use of wetted, nbpt-treated prilled urea (Wetted prilled urea) instead of granular urea, regardless of the initial soil N fertility. Provided N application frequency remains unchanged, this will result in considerable cost savings.

The Wetted prilled urea technology in conjunction with VRA, has shown that significantly lower rates of N application can be achieved on commercial dairy farms without impacting milk production, or tonnes DM grown, provided irrigation management is not compromised. Cost reductions appear to be achievable provided close attention is paid to the number of application applied. If the budgeted reductions to nitrogen inputs (40%) and costs (30%) can be achieved without any loss to pasture production, this will provide a real pathway for dairy farms to significantly improve the environmental impact of their N applications with no reduction in on-farm profits. The full two year's results will allow much stronger and more specific conclusions to be drawn.

References

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